

DIGITAL INDIA: A REVIEW OF CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

In an order to create participative, transparent and responsive government, the rise of e-government has been one of the most striking developments of the web. As the Internet supported digital communities evolve, and assuming that they do indeed grow to incorporate individuals around the country (and globe) , they present the national governments with a number of challenges and opportunities . Digital India is an initiative by the Government of India to ensure that Government services are made available to citizens electronically by improving online infrastructure and by increasing Internet connectivity. It was launched on 1 July 2015 by Prime Minister Narendra Modi. The initiative includes plans to connect rural areas with high-speed internet networks. Digital India has three core components. These include: The creation of digital infrastructure i.e. Delivering services digitally , Digital literacy.

Keywords: Digital India, Government, citizens, digital infrastructure.

INTRODUCTION

The term e-government was first used in the United States in 1993 (Heeks & Bailur, 2007). E-Government or ‘electronic government’ is comprised of three main activities: the improvement in efficiency and effectiveness of the functions of government, including the delivery of services to citizens; the increase in transparency of government through the provision of a greater range of information; and the fundamental change in relationship between citizens and public sector organisations (Bellamy and Taylor, 1994; Li, 2003; Watson and Mundy, 2001).

There are currently a large number of definitions of electronic government. It has been defined by different authors in many different ways in the literature (Moon, 2002; Yildiz, 2007). West (2004), for example, defines e-government as the delivery of government information and services through the internet or other digital means. Schuppan (2009) defines e-government as a way of strengthening the public sector performance for accomplishing social and economic

developments in a country. E-government promises significant benefits to governments and their citizens including delivery of quality public service, convenience and accessibility to government services, improvement of the quality of life, reduction of communication and information costs, bridging digital divide, and active participation of citizens in government (Aldrich et al. 2002; Jaeger and Thompson 2003). Thus, e-government can be viewed as a subset of e-governance, and its focus is largely on improving administrative efficiency and reducing administrative corruption (Bhatnagar Subhash, 2004). However, no matter how e-government is defined, the ultimate goal of e-government is to create public values for citizens .

E-Governance

E-governance is the application of information & communication technologies to transform the efficiency, effectiveness, transparency and accountability of informational & transactional exchanges with in government, between govt. & govt. agencies of National, State, Municipal & Local levels, citizen & businesses, and to empower citizens through access & use of information.

e-governance evolution : History and Present Status

Global shifts towards increased deployment of IT by governments emerged in the nineties, with the advent of the World Wide Web. The technology as well as e-governance initiatives have come a long way since then. With the increase in Internet and mobile connections, the citizens are learning to exploit their new mode of access in wide ranging ways. They have started expecting more and more information and services online from governments and corporate organizations to further their civic, professional and personal lives , thus creating abundant evidence that the new “e-citizenship” is taking hold.

The concept of e-governance has its origins in India during the seventies with a focus on development of in- house government applications in the areas of defense, economic monitoring, planning and the deployment of IT to manage data intensive functions related to elections, census, tax administration etc. The efforts of the National Informatics Center (NIC) to connect all the district headquarters during the eighties was a very significant development. From the early nineties, IT technologies were supplemented by ICT technologies to extend its use for

wider sectoral applications with policy emphasis on reaching out to rural areas and taking in greater inputs from NGOs and private sector as well. There has been an increasing involvement of international donor agencies under the framework of e-governance for development to catalyze the development of e-governance laws and technologies in developing countries..

While the emphasis has been primarily on automation and computerization, state governments have also endeavored to use ICT tools into connectivity, networking, setting up systems for processing information and delivering services. At a micro level, this has ranged from IT automation in individual departments, electronic file handling and workflow systems, access to entitlements, public grievance systems, service delivery for high volume routine transactions such as payment of bills, tax dues to meeting poverty alleviation goals through the promotion of entrepreneurial models and provision of market information. The thrust has varied across initiatives, with some focusing on enabling the citizen-state interface for various government services, and others focusing on bettering livelihoods. Every state govt. has taken the initiative to form an IT task force to outline IT policy document for the state and the citizen charters have started appearing on govt. websites.

Project

The Government of India entity Bharat Broadband Network Limited which executes the National Optical Fibre Network project will be the custodian of Digital India (DI) project.[3][4] BBNL had ordered United Telecoms Limited to connect 250,000 villages through GPON to ensure FTTH based broadband. This will provide the first basic setup to achieve towards Digital India and is expected to be completed by 2017.

The government is planning to create 28,000 seats of BPOs in various states and set up at least one Common Service Centre in each of the gram panchayats in the state.[5]

Ravi Shankar Prasad announced on 27 February 2016 that National Institute of Electronics and Information Technology (NIELIT) would be set up in Kurukshetra to provide computer training to youth and a Software Technology Park of India (STPI) would be set up in Panchkula's existing HSIIDC IT Park in Sector 23.[5]

The 2016 Union budget of India announced 11 technology initiatives including the use data analytics to nab tax evaders, creating a substantial opportunity for IT companies to build out the systems that will be required.[6] Digital Literacy mission will cover six crore rural households.[6] It is planned to connect 550 farmer markets in the country through the use of technology.[7].

Following are some of the recent e-governance projects implemented by various state govts.

State/Union Territory	Initiatives covering departmental automation, user charge collection, delivery of policy/programme information and delivery of entitlements
Andhra Pradesh	e-Seva, CARD, VOICE, MPHS, FAST, e-Cops, AP online—One-stop-shop on the Internet, Saukaryam, Online Transaction processing
Bihar	Sales Tax Administration Management Information
Chattisgarh	Chhattisgarh Infotech Promotion Society, Treasury office, e-linking project
Delhi	Automatic Vehicle Tracking System, Computerisation of website of RCS office, Electronic Clearance System, Management Information System for Education etc
Goa	Dharani Project
Gujarat	Mahiti Shakti, request for Government documents online, Form book online, G R book online, census online, tender notice.
Haryana	Nai Disha
Himachal Pradesh	Lok Mitra

Karnataka	Bhoomi, Khajane, Kaveri
Kerala	e-Srinkhala, RDNet, Fast, Reliable, Instant, Efficient Network for the Disbursement of Services (FRIENDS)
Madhya Pradesh	Gyandoot, Gram Sampark, Smart Card in Transport Department, Computerization MP State Agricultural Marketing Board (Mandi Board) etc
Maharashtra	SETU, Online Complaint Management System—Mumbai
Rajasthan	Jan Mitra, RajSWIFT, Lokmitra, RajNIDHI
Tamil Nadu	Rasi Maiyams–Kanchipuram; Application forms related to public utility, tender notices and display

North-Eastern States

Arunachal Pradesh,	Community Information Center. Forms available on
Manipur,	the Meghalaya website under schemes related to
Meghalaya,	
Mizoram & Nagaland	social welfare, food civil supplies and consumer affairs, housing transport etc.

Pillars for e-governance

The Government of India hopes to achieve growth on multiple fronts with the Digital India Programme. Specifically, the government aims to target nine 'Pillars of Digital India' that they identify as being: [8]

1. Broadband Highways
2. Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity
3. Public Internet Access Programme
4. e-Governance – Reforming Government through Technology

5. eKranti - Electronic delivery of services
6. Information for All
7. Electronics Manufacturing
8. IT for Jobs
9. Early Harvest Programmes

e-Governance Action Plan – Strategies for today; Vision for Future

Govt. leaders in India are starting to realize that e-governance is the key to drive today's economy with an increased participation from citizens. Providing services online is no longer going to remain optional for local and central government as demand for providing services at internet speed has been coming from the citizens.

In this era of accountability and performance measurement, govts. will face increasing pressure to make the services more accessible to their citizens. The pressure comes directly from the new legislatures and govt. policies to implement high-end technologies in governing the nations; but also indirectly and perhaps more intensely from citizens. The citizens now a days are not using govt. services in isolation, but are simultaneously making transactions and interacting with the corporate world. In addition to this direct or indirect pressure, governments must themselves study & realize the cost saving benefits e-Governance techniques produce. With this rise in demand for e-services, it is a mandatory requirement for government budget writers that the efficiency enhancement and cost saving potential of providing online services and information be mastered.

E-governance is about more than streamlining processes and improving services. It's about transforming Governments and renovating the way citizens participate in democracy. So how does a government agency cut through the clutter and build a strategy to facilitate the transition to successful online or "e" service delivery. If the govt. waits, it's perceived as being out of touch with the citizen needs and loses an opportunity to realize the tremendous benefits of online service delivery and larger citizen participation in overall service delivery. Yet if the e-governance started and implemented in haste, they are doomed to fail. According to one of the surveys conducted by a reputed agency, 75% of e-governance may fail because of poor planning

The real challenges is how to develop and sustain successful e-governance projects and deliver state of the art e-services to citizens. Unfortunately its not as easy as adding “e” in front of your service delivery mechanism. Successful e-governance initiatives can never be taken in haste. Particularly for the democratic nation of the billion people like India, e-Governance should enable seamless access to information and seamless flow of information across the state and central government in the federal setup. No country has so far implemented an e-governance system for one billion people. Some of the requirements for implementing successful e-governance across the nation are :

- e-Governance framework across the nation with enough bandwidth to service a population of one billion.
- Connectivity framework for making the services reach rural areas of the country or development of alternative means of services such as e-governance kiosks in regional languages.
- National Citizen database which is the primary unit of data for all governance vertical and horizontal applications across the state and central governments.
- E-governance and interoperability standards for the exchange of secure information with non-repudiation, across the state and central government departments seamlessly.
- A secure delivery framework by means of virtual private network connecting across the state and central government departments.
- Datacenters in centre and states to handle the departmental workflow automation, collaboration, interaction, exchange of information with authentication.

Ten Points PM Narendra Modi Made on Digital India

1. E-governance is going to change to M-Governance soon. 'M' is not for 'Modi', but 'Mobile'.

2. Make in India is important but 'Design in India' equally important for digital India. We need to create products in different languages and age group. It is a market of 125 crore people.
3. Digital India will enable investment of Rs. 4.5 lakh crore and ensure jobs for 18 lakh people.
4. Like bank lockers, there will be digital godowns where we will keep all our important documents.
5. Now people will settle down only at places with an optical fibre network.
6. Even a child understands digital power. Earlier, a child used to playfully wrench your reading glasses. Today, he reaches for your phone.
7. I dream of digital India where the world looks to India for the next big Idea.
8. I dream of a digital India where high-speed digital highways unite the nation, where 1.2 billion connected Indians drive innovation.
9. Can we secure the world from the bloodless war? I'm talking about Cyber security. India must take the lead in cyber security through innovation.
10. India has about 25 crore internet users. But the people who are still not using internet are more than anywhere else.

Services under digital India

Some of the facilities which will be provided through this initiative are Digital Locker, e-education, e-health, e-sign and national scholarship portal. As the part of Digital India, Indian government planned to launch Botnet cleaning centers.[9]

Digi Locker

Digital Locker facility will help citizens to digitally store their important documents like PAN card, passport, mark sheets and degree certificates. Digital Locker will provide secure access to Government issued documents. It uses authenticity services provided by Aadhaar. It is aimed at

eliminating the use of physical documents and enables sharing of verified electronic documents across government agencies.[10][11][12]

Attendance.gov.in

Attendance.gov.in is a website, launched by PM Narendra Modi on 1 July 2015[1] to keep a record of the attendance of Government employees on a real-time basis.[13] This initiative started with implementation of a common Biometric Attendance System (BAS) in the central government offices located in Delhi.[14]

MyGov.in

MyGov.in is a platform to share inputs and ideas on matters of policy and governance.[15]

Railways

Under the Digital India programme, 3 applications viz. handheld terminals for Indian Railways travelling ticket examiners (TTEs), a paperless unreserved ticketing mobile application and a facility for E-booking of disposable linen on trains were launched by Railways Minister Suresh Prabhu on 10 February 2016.[16][17]

Partnerships

Digital India Week

At the launch ceremony of Digital India Week by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, top CEOs from India and abroad committed to invest ₹4.5 lakh crore (US\$66 billion) towards this initiative. The CEOs said the investments would be utilized towards making smartphones and internet devices at an affordable price in India which would help generate jobs in India as well as reduce the cost of importing them from abroad.[18]

Reliance Industries Chairman Mukesh Ambani said his company would invest ₹2.5 lakh crore (US\$37 billion) across different Digital India heads, which have the potential to create employment for over five lakh people. He also announced setting up of the 'Jio Digital India Start Up Fund' to encourage young entrepreneurs who are setting up businesses focused around the Digital India initiative.[18] Bharti Group chief Sunil Mittal committed investments of more than ₹1 lakh crore (US\$15 billion) in the next five years to create deeper infrastructure in rural and urban India in the areas of e-health and e-education.[19]

Silicon Valley

Giants from Silicon Valley, San Jose, California expressed their support for Digital India during PM Narendra Modi's visit in September 2015. Facebook's CEO, Mark Zuckerberg, changed his profile picture in support of Digital India and started a chain on Facebook and promised to work on WiFi Hotspots in rural area of India.[20] Google committed to provide broadband connectivity on 500 railway stations in India. Microsoft agreed to provide broadband connectivity to five hundred thousand villages in India and make India its cloud hub through Indian data centres. Qualcomm announced an investment of US\$150 million in Indian startups.[21] Oracle plans to invest in 20 states and will work on payments and Smart city initiatives.[22] However back home in India, cyber experts expressed their concern over internet.org and viewed the Prime Minister's bonhomie with Zuckerberg as the government's indirect approval of the controversial initiative.[23] Saket Suman, in his report in The Statesman mentioned, "Prime Minister Narendra Modi's chemistry with Facebook CEO Mark Zuckerberg at the social media giant's headquarters in California may have been greeted enthusiastically in Silicon Valley but back home several social media enthusiasts and cyber activists are disappointed." [24] Later the Prime Minister office clarified that net neutrality will be maintained at all costs and vetoed the Basic Internet plans.[23]

Campaign

Times Now and ET Now have announced the launch of the second edition of Digital India Summit & Awards on 22 March 2016.[25]

The Gauhati University (GU)'s National Service Scheme (NSS), along with the Centre's department of electronics and information technology, recently organized a workshop on Digital India on the university campus.[26] Twenty universities across the country, including GU, were selected in the first phase of the university-level Digital India scheme to conduct workshops on Prime Minister Narendra Modi's pet project.[26] A total of 25 colleges, 300 NSS volunteers and 25 NSS programme officers joined the workshop.[26]

Performance

In 2015, India crossed a new Internet milestone of 375 million Internet users, which exceeds the population of the US, making it the world's second largest country by the number of Internet users after China.[27] More than half of these users access the Internet through a mobile phone.[27] India was ranked 131 out of 167 countries in the recent Information and Communications Technology (ICT) Development Index.[27] 928 million National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) transactions worth ₹60 trillion (US\$880 billion) were made in 2014-15 as against 661 million transactions worth ₹44 trillion (US\$650 billion) the previous year.[27] Optical fibre cables have been laid out in more than 68000 village panchayats.[28] Doing away with past practices, railways has made e-auction mandatory for scrap auction as part of the Digital India initiative even as it made over ₹30 billion (US\$440 million) from such sales in 2014-15.[29]

On 28 December 2015, the Panchkula district of Haryana was awarded for being the top performing district in the state under the Digital India campaign.[30] The Common Service Centres (CSCs) have been upgraded in all districts and the number of e-services has now reached 105, which includes application of new water connection, sewer connection, electricity bill collection, ration card member registration, result of HBSE, admit cards for board examinations, online admission form for government colleges, long route booking of buses, admission forms for Kurukshetra University and HUDA plots status inquiry.[5] Haryana has become the first state to implement Aadhaar-enabled birth registration in all the districts.[5]

For success of an e-governance project and superior service delivery, it is imperative that the government agency focuses on whole citizen experience. Focusing on the citizen is essential for long term success. The govt. agency needs to integrate information from all points of citizen interaction. The overall architecture for e-Governance needs to ensure that the architecture components are extensible and scalable to adapt to the changing environments. The e-Governance applications that are emerging as islands of successes have to be interoperable. Following are some of the suggestions for the successful transformation from “ A” to “e”

a) Create Literacy and commitment to e-governance at high level

The most important requirement is a training program for policy makers in E-Governance (Senior Public Servants), politicians and IT task force members. The training program needs to be focused according to the requirements of the policy makers at the top. Such programs can be

need based and outsourced when required. In addition it should be made mandatory for all the stake holders in implementation and maintenance of e-governance services to have the general IT skills. There may be specific requirements for training in certain specific projects. Such programs can be need based and outsourced when required. A few suggestive programs include e-governance training, Building web interfaces for citizen interaction, Document management and workflow applications, security and PKI solutions, Office Automation, networking etc.

b) Conduct Usability Surveys for assessment of existing e-governance projects

There is a varying degree of development of e-governance among the different states. A few States have leapfrogged into a digital era whereas a few are yet to start with any initiative. There is a tremendous divergence in the extent of implementation of the concept of e-Governance. It is, therefore, not possible to come up with a framework for implementation of e-Governance which is straightaway applicable to all states and the Central Government. Therefore an e-readiness exercise should be carried out in all states, government departments to understand their level of acceptability of the e-governance.

c) Starting with implementation of pilot projects and replicating the successful ones

The pilot projects taken in various states should be assessed for their achievement levels. They should be classified as success or failure according to the desired output written down before implementation of the projects. The study should be carried out by an independent agency for the implementation agency The study should be carried out at each stage of implementation. Bottlenecks and causes of delays should be documented, even though they are removed later. The successful projects should be replicated over the nation with members drawn from the implementing team. The projects, which could not achieve the desired outcome, should be documented for possible causes of failure. Various bottlenecks and causes of delay should be identified.

d) Follow the Best Practices in e-governance

The study of Best Practices will bring forward the best practices being followed nationally and internationally. The national and international Best Practices study will give a great momentum

to the process of E-Governance. The State Governments will not have to re-invent wheel every time and they can learn from the developments already made.

e) Build National resource Database of e-governance projects

This would allow any organization planning an IT project to instantly ascertain whether any such project has already been implemented anywhere in the country. Intending implementers would know who the key people in similar projects are and how to reach them. It is well known that it is much easier to replicate a solution than to evolve it the first time around. So the lead-time to implement projects can be reduced substantially.

If a project is already in operation in a similar environment somewhere in the country, acceptance by all concerned is much faster and smoother elsewhere. So change management becomes much easier and the time and effort involved in such implementations. Due recognition would accrue to the pioneers who created the successes. It would enable others to learn from them if they wish.

For implementing agencies, be they Government owned organizations like NIC, CDAC and State PSUs or private IT companies, it offers a unique opportunity to derive the full return and reward, both domestically and internationally, from their successes and the IPRs/ products that they have created. It would help create an archive of e-governance applications in the country.

f) Have clearly defined Interoperability policy

The e-governance architecture needs to ensure that the components are scalable and adaptable to the future requirements. It has also to ensure that the Local architecture fits into the State level and the same into National and Global architecture. Interoperability is a major criterion while defining the architecture.

g) Manage and Update content on govt. websites efficiently and regularly

Content is the 'heart' of any IT project. The govt. agency has to keep in mind some of the important technical guidelines, while developing the software and computerization, to facilitate the future integration. The department also needs to address the security of transactions and messages. The process of content development encompasses a whole range of activities starting with a comprehensive study of the system and identification of the objectives. It ends up with

delivery of the intended benefits to the citizens or other users of the IT System. The govt. agencies must ensure that the data on the sites is always updated and relevant.

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